

**IMMIGRANT IDENTITY AND DIASPORIC CONSCIOUSNESS IN
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Akola****Received: 18/11/13****Reviewed: 20/11/13****Accepted: 23/11/13****Research Paper in English****Abstract:**

In the second half of the 20th century, popularly known as post-colonial period, the experiences of migrants or diasporic people have become an integral part of discussion in modern literary intelligentsia and contemporary societies. We can say that the writings of diasporic writers have been at the forefront of recent literary discussion seeking to articulate the experiences of expatriated people. Diasporic writing has raised questions regarding the definitions of 'home' and 'nation'. The Indian diasporic writings have become a distinctive class with the arrival of such writers as V.S. Naipaul, Salman Rushdie, Bharati Mukherjee, Kamala Markandaya, Balachandra Rajan Vikram Seth, Jhumpha Lihir M.G. Vassanji, Uma Parameswaran. Schizophrenia and/or nostalgia are often the preoccupations of these writers as they seek to locate themselves in new cultures. It becomes important to question the nature of their relationship with the work of writers and literatures of the country of their origin and to examine the different strategies they adopt in order to negotiate the cultural space of the countries of their adoption. The present paper focuses on the term diaspora and attempts to examine the immigrant identity and diasporic consciousness as reflected in "The Namesake" by Jhumpa Lahiri. Being the first novel of Lahiri, The Namesake reveals the emotional and cultural dilemma of the writer. Lahiri has exploited her own experiences in the novel.

**Key words: Diaspora Consciousness,
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In the second half of the 20th century, popularly known as post-colonial period, the experiences of migrant or diasporic people have become an integral part of discussion in modern literary intelligentsia and contemporary societies. We can say that the writings of diasporic writers have been at the forefront of recent literary discussion seeking to articulate the experiences of expatriated people. The term 'diaspora' was derived from the Greek word that means 'to sow' or 'to disperse'. It is used to refer to "any people or ethnic population forced or induced to leave their traditional ethnic homelands, being dispersed throughout other parts of

the world, and the ensuing developments in their dispersal and culture". It is concerned with the people who are away from their origin, home and nation.

Robin Cohen (2008) has pointed out the four phases of Diaspora studies as follow:

In the first phase, the term Diaspora was mainly confined to the study of the Jewish experience. Later on, from the 1960s and 1970s the meaning of the term was systematically extended, becoming more common as a description of the dispersion of Africans, Armenians and the Irish. With the Jews, these peoples conceived their scattering as arising from a cataclysmic event that had traumatized the group as a whole. Retrospectively and

without complete consensus, the Palestinians were later added to this group.

In the second phase, in the 1980s and onwards, as Safran notably argued, diaspora was deployed as 'a metaphoric designation' to describe different categories of people – 'expatriates, expellees, political refugees, alien residents, immigrants and ethnic and racial minorities tout court'. Moreover, a point again made by Safran, the term now designated a vast array of different peoples who either applied the term to themselves or had the label conferred upon them. Given their number (certainly now over one hundred), their historical experiences, collective narratives and differing relationships to homelands and hostlands, they were bound to be a more varied cluster of diasporas than the groups designated in phase one.

The third phase, from the mid-1990s, was marked by social constructionist critiques of 'second phase' theorists who, despite their recognition of the proliferation of groups newly designated as diasporas and the evolution of new ways of studying them, were still seen as holding back the full force of the concept. Influenced by postmodernist readings, social constructionists sought to decompose two of the major building blocks previously delimiting and demarcate (separate) the diasporic idea, namely 'homeland' and 'ethnic/religious community'. In the postmodern world, it was further argued, identities have become constructed and deconstructed in a flexible and situational way; accordingly, concepts of diaspora had to be radically reordered in response to this complexity.

By the turn of the century, the current phase of consolidation set in. The social constructionist critiques were partially accommodated, but were seen as in danger of emptying the notion of diaspora of much of its analytical and descriptive power. While the increased complexity of identities is valid phenomena, ideas of home remains powerful discourses. This phase of consolidation is marked by a modified reaffirmation of the diasporic idea, including its core elements, common features and ideal types.

Indian Diaspora

The story of cultural exchanges that people of India had and have with the rest of the world is fascinating one. During the ancient times, saints and monks undertook the long journeys for the spread of knowledge, peace and love. Even the archeological evidences have proved the fact that Indians during ancient period did travel to other countries for trade. The navigational skills of people along the Indian coastal cities helped the rulers to expand the horizons of their Kingdoms.

There were large scale movement of people occurred when Islam arrived in India. During this period those rulers who returned to their countries after plundering India took thousands of men and women especially artists, architects, calligraphers, musicians, dancers, courtesans along with them. During the colonial period, Indians were traded as slaves by Portuguese, Dutch, French and English imperialists. The Indians were taken to various countries as indentured labourers to develop plantation, economies, to construct railway networks and to serve as soldiers in the imperial military

establishments. Large number of traders and professionals also accompanied these labourers and soldiers.

The first set of scholars and academics came out from the universities of independent India migrated to western countries for higher education, advanced studies and research form the first diaspora in modern period. Out of this emerged the Indian Diasporic writing. The Indian diasporic writings have become a distinctive class with the arrival of such writers as V.S. Naipaul, Salman Rushdie, Bharati Mukherjee, Kamala Markandaya, Balachandra Rajan Vikram Seth, Jhumpa Lahiri M.G. Vassanji, Uma Parameswaran. Their writings have raised questions regarding the definitions of 'home' and 'nation'. The search of migrant identity, self-identity, myth about home, and nostalgia are often the preoccupations of these writers as they seek to locate themselves in new cultures.

Immigrant Identity and Diasporic Consciousness in Jhumpa Lahiri's "The Namesake"

Jhumpa Lahiri (1967) was born in London. She is the daughter of Indian immigrants from the state of West Bengal. Her family moved to the United States when she was just two. From her childhood, she experienced the various conflicts related to the diasporic identity. When she began pre primary education in Kingston, Rhode Island, Lahiri's teacher would call her by her pet name, Jhumpa, because it was easier to pronounce than her proper names. Lahiri recalled that event in her life; she says "I always felt so embarrassed by my name.... You feel like you're causing someone pain just by being who you are." In her works, she has tried

to emphasize on the struggle of immigrants or diasporic people for their real cultural identity. The people migrate from their homeland to fulfill their dreams and to get more opportunities in developing their standard of living. However, the experiences of all migrants are not pleasant, some experience the internal agony and feel nostalgic. Lahiri's "The Namesake" reflects her diasporic consciousness The ambivalence over her own identity was the inspiration for the ambivalence of identity of Gogol, the protagonist of her novel *The Namesake*, over his unusual name.

The Namesake (2003) is the first novel by Jhumpa Lahiri. It was originally a novella published in *The New Yorker* and was later expanded to a full length novel. It explores many of the same emotional and cultural themes as her Pulitzer Prize-winning short story collection *Interpreter of Maladies*. The action of the novel moves in Calcutta, Boston, and New York City. The novel examines the dilemma of the characters that are caught between two conflicting cultures with highly distinct religious, social, and ideological differences.

It is story of an immigrant family Ashima and Ashoke from Calcutta, India that has recently settled in Cambridge, Massachusetts. The beginning of the story is itself enough to reflect the diasporic consciousness in writer's mind. The novel opens with the entry of Ashima who is trying to make some spicy Indian snacks by using American combinations of salt, lemon, and thin slice of green chilli pepper. But when she tastes it, she realizes that something is missing in it. "Tasting from a cupped palm, she frowns; as usual,

there's something missing" (1) Jhumpa Lahiri, through the condition of Ashima Ganguly, tries to show the condition of an Indian immigrant who is struggling to understand the new taste of the new culture but fails to find out as they still carry out their home identity.

Their story begins in actual sense with the birth of their first child; the reader instantly becomes aware of the obstacles facing the Ganguli family. The difficulties Ashima and Ashoke face in America are best articulated by Ashima herself when she says, "For being a foreigner, Ashima is beginning to realize, is sort of lifelong pregnancy—a perpetual wait, a constant burden, a continuous feeling out of sorts" (49). This sentiment is expressed early on in the work and makes the reader aware that life in America will be a constant struggle. However unlike immigrants during the early 1900's, the problems the Ganguli's face will be less physical and material (the prospect of finding work and housing), and more psychological. Ashima, who is with-child at the beginning of the story, is already extremely fragile and naturally feels more vulnerable in her pregnant state. Her insights during this tumultuous time in her life are extremely important if one is to understand the significance of her journey and the emotional stress it has on her. As Ashima waits to give birth she yearns for her life back in Calcutta. She remarks that in India a mother giving birth would be surrounded by family and friends. The atmosphere in India then, is much more intimate than in Cambridge, where everything feels less personal and "colder" than back home. With only Ashoke at her side, Ashima's feeling of isolation is obvious as she

wonders whether she might be the only Indian woman in the hospital giving birth that day.

Once the baby is born, the parents are faced with the prospect of naming their newborn son. Here again, the clash between Indian and American culture or Diasporic dilemma is demonstrated. In India, a child would be called by a "pet name", an informal name used by family and friends. Meanwhile, the name listed on official documents is called the child's "good name". In India, this name wouldn't be important right away, and parents would sometimes take years before deciding on a child's good name. Ashima and Ashoke give Ashima's grandmother the honor of officially naming their son, but the letter from India is lost in the mail. The Ganguli's want to wait for the letter to arrive (it never does), but before they leave they have to provide a name on a birth certificate. Finally, they decide on the name, "Gogol", representing a Russian author whose name played a large part in Ashoke's history before coming to the United States. The struggle the parents have here with the naming of their child is obvious, but it also symbolizes the disconnect and distance Ashima and Ashoke feel with the rest of the world. They feel close to neither their new home nor the one they left behind.

Although Ashima and Ashoke's experience in America is of vital importance, the novel would not be complete if it didn't follow their son Gogol's life's journey. In the end, the narrator is able to make a judgment about Gogol and how he lived that is very telling. "He had spent years maintaining distance from his origins; his parent, in

bridging that distance as best they could. And yet, for all his aloofness toward his family in the past...he has never been more than a four-hour train ride away"(281). This quote is important because it represents the approach Gogol had to his heritage throughout the novel. Unlike his parents, Gogol goes out of his way to avoid his Indian culture. For example, Gogol's personal life he dates white American women, while befriending mostly Caucasian males. These choices disturb Gogol's parents, especially Ashima who wishes he would settle down with another Indian woman. Paying no attention to her wishes, Gogol maintains distance from his parents throughout his adult life, even if he is always close by. He often waits days to return their phone calls, misses important events to go to his girlfriends' summer homes, and does his best to never embrace the culture that his parents cherish.

These habits are important, but pale in comparison to an action that was a blatant attempt to escape his Indian heritage. When Gogol was in his twenty's he changed his name to a more Americanized Indian name: Nikhil. As extreme as this was, it is more important to note that Nikhil never truly lost the "Gogol" inside of him. In the end, Nikhil realizes that running away from his roots is futile and not gratifying. "Without people in the world to call him Gogol, no matter how long he himself lives, Gogol Ganguli will, once and for all, vanish from the lips of loved ones, and so, cease to exist. Yet the thought of this eventual demise provides no sense of victory, no solace. It provides no solace at all" (289). This quote represents one of the main ideas of the

book: Gogol, as hard as he tried to run away from his family and Indian culture, was bound by an invisible thread to India and its customs. Despite the influence of pop culture, white girlfriends, and a name change, Gogol couldn't escape. In fact, by the end he realizes that he doesn't want to leave his heritage behind. "Things that should never have happened, that seemed out of place and wrong, these were what prevailed, what endured, in the end" (287). Gogol realizes that everything that has happened to him, from the botched naming attempt at his birth, to his father's death, was meaningful. In the end, the very thing that Gogol was running away from becomes the cornerstone of his life. In fact, even if Gogol never knew it, it always was.

Author Jhumpa Lahiri accomplished something that every writer strives for. She created an engaging piece of literature that has meaning and can speak to everyone. Following the lives of an immigrant family from Calcutta, *The Namesake* accurately characterizes the struggles and successes of the Ganguli's as they adjust to life in America. For Ashima and Ashoke, their journey meant learning to balance their newfound American culture with all-important Indian traditions. For Gogol however, it was realizing the significance of his heritage, of his "namesake", that characterized his journey. Lahiri never lead the reader to believe any of these adjustments were easy, which is why the novel is able to deliver its message so powerfully. The challenges facing the Ganguli family were never sugar coated, or presented as if they were as simple as putting up a tree around Christmas time. Instead, the journey is raw

and realistic, making the final destination that much more meaningful.

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